

Online Learning Environment in Education: Constructivist And Cooperative Approach Of Learning

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Abstract:

Constructivist approach of learning is based on the assumption that quality learning depends on the nature of student involvement with activities and conditions likely to generate learning. Learning environment is the quality of effort students themselves devote to educationally purposeful activities that contribute directly to desired outcomes. Further, it promises that education is fundamentally about students' creation of their own knowledge. While students are seen to be responsible for constructing their knowledge, learning is also seen to depend on institution and staff generating conditions that stimulate and encourage student environment. Within the last decade, online technologies have grown from a volatile childhood to a point at which they are starting to make a serious impression on pattern of learning and teaching in higher education, in many areas pervasive adoption and deployment of online learning technologies is challenging. Online technologies have enriched student learning by opening access to a greater learning by opening access to a greater range of interactive resources, making course content more cognitively accessible, providing automated and adaptive forms of assessment. Further, online tools allow students to interact with learning materials, their peers and enter university in ways that are not bound by time or place. So, this paper is regarding the incorporation of constructivist and cooperative approach in online learning.

Key Words: Online learning, cooperative learning, constructivist approach

Introduction: Constructivism refers to a process where the learners actively construct their own knowledge by connecting new ideas with existing ideas. The learner constructs, a new version of reality from their own unique experiences and it is the construction which they use to deal with any new experiences in that field. The following are four important characteristics of **constructivism**:

Focus on learning through posing problems, exploring possible answers and developing products and presentations. Pursue global goals that specify general abilities such as problem solving and research skills. Stress more group work i.e cooperative learning than individualized work. Emphasizes alternative learning and assessment methods; exploration of open-ended questions and scenarios, doing research and developing products; assessment by student portfolios, performance checklist, and test with open-ended questions and descriptive narratives written by teachers. It is pertinent to say that present education system across the world higher education is dominantly dependent on the teacher directed instruction where knowledge is considered as a commodity and teacher transmits to students in a fully formal and structured environment by giving verbal lecture. Further, students are expected to retrieve the information, knowledge and skills as taught by the teachers without having sufficient understanding. It is an undeniable fact that teacher directed instruction is useful in many specific situations namely skill training, in procedural matter but ultimate goals of education are Constructivist by nature along with cooperative techniques of

learning. The outcomes of education especially if it is taken in lifelong perspectives of learning are more likely to be key board capabilities such as thinking critically and making judgments, solving problems and developing plans, performing procedures and demonstrate techniques, managing and developing oneself, accessing and managing information, demonstrating knowledge and understanding designing, creating and performing and communicating. The development of these capabilities is an interactive process which continues indefinitely, The development of aforementioned capabilities demand a separate version of learning environment where teaching and learning process will emphasize the following activities and premises. Making skills more relevant to student background and experiences by anchoring learning tasks in meaningful, authentic highly visual situations. Addressing and motivating problem through interactive activities in which students must play active rather than passive roles. Teaching students how to work together to solve problems through group based collaborative and cooperative learning activities. Emphasizing and engaging students in motivational activities that require higher level skills and prerequisite lower level skills at the same time. Selection of activities, tools and environments that will encourage metacognition. self awareness, self analysis, self regulation and self reflection Learning environment, content and tasks need to be relevant, realistic and represent the natural complexities of the real world Primary source of data will be used to provide authenticity and real world complexity. If it is the

main contention that the learning environment of higher education must be resource based and highly productive which can actively involve the learner in process of knowledge construction, the author would like to say that we would no longer rely on the existing learning environment of conventional university for knowledge generation in the age of advance technologies- Online technologies have already occupied a place in distance education to overcome its inherited weakness of poor or no interaction among teachers and students; student and with their peers. If these technologies will be integrated for learning purpose at off campus university level, can overcome prevailing boring and unproductive learning atmosphere.

Need of Online Learning Environment

As present higher education is facing increasing pressure to produce knowledge workers who can participate in contemporary developed economies to respond to perceived commercial and competition dynamics and improve quality standards. The aforementioned demands have forced university education to anchor on fixed institutional time tables and grouping together (cooperative) students in batches. Students are being given greater flexibility to vary the rhythm of their learning. Even more powerful and pervasive information and communication technologies are supplementing or replacing white boards, overhead project/ and printed materials. Constructivist and cooperative pedagogical theories have started to have a real influence on instructional practices in lectures, laboratories and tutorials. Student are being seen as clients rather than passive recipients of university activities. Further, contemporary online learning technologies have been identified as particularly important agents of change. Observers now comment on the inexorable changes marked by emerging technologies in 21st Century. The inherited fabric of higher education is under strain around the world Increasingly pervasive information and communication technologies are enabling people to think differently about the ways in which higher learning is conceptualized, designed, developed and delivered. In particular the digital revolution is both creating and surveying a demand for online learning environment and novel pedagogies.

Online Learning Environment and Constructivism along with Cooperative Learning: Constructivist approach of learning is based on the assumption that quality learning depends on the nature of student involvement with activities and conditions likely to generate learning. Learning environment is the quality of effort students themselves devote to educationally purposeful activities that contribute directly to desired outcomes. Further, it promises that education is fundamentally about students' creation

of their own knowledge While students are seen to be responsible for constructing their knowledge, learning is also seen to depend on institution and staff generating conditions that stimulate and encouraged student environment Within the last decade, online technologies have grown from a volatile childhood to a point at which they are starting to make a serious impression on pattern of learning and teaching in higher education, in many areas pervasive adoption and deployment of online learning technologies is challenging. Online technologies have enriched student learning by opening across to a greater learning by opening access to a greater range of interactive resources, making course content more cognitively accessible, providing automated and adoptive forms of assessment. Further, online tools allow students to interact with learning materials, their peers and enter university in ways that are not bound by time or place. Review of the literature on learning effectiveness of online courses provided excellent evidence that Online discussion may be more supportive of experimentation, divergent thinking and exploration of multiple perspectives, complex understanding and reflection than face to face discussion and Online discussion may be less supportive of convergent thinking, teacher directed inquiry and specific thinking than face to face discussion.

If we adhere to constructivist principles, there is evidence that online learning can be supportive. Online learning system provides resources and facilities that can enrich student learning. They are seen to reinforce and enhance constructivist pedagogies. Online learning technologies can enrich education by allowing students access to a greater range of resource and materials. It is further agreed that internet technologies can be used to make course contents cognitively accessible to individual learners by allowing them to interact with diverse dynamics, associative and ready to hand knowledge networks. Online technologies may also enrich learning by providing automated and adoptive formative assessment which can be individually initiated and administered.

Steps to Strengthen Online Learning Environment

Constructive learning depends on constructive teaching. Teaching environment needs to be authentic and self supportive and encourage individual learning. The desire to create a constructive teaching and learning environment in higher education implies the need for adoptive, interactive and multifaceted pedagogies which support the activity and agency of the individual student. Hence, the essential activities and transactional strategies on which online learning technologies need to be focused to trigger constructive pedagogies are as follows:

- 1. Emphasis on contextualized learning:** Constructivism assumes that maximum learning occurs when it takes place in real life context. Thus online learning technologies must enable the learners for exploration of knowledge, experience and skill within a framework resembling actual practice or real life situation, so that they can easily apply the knowledge gained in formal situation to an informal situation and vice versa. Further, they can internalize what is outside and then externalize what is internal.
 - 2. Encourage active learning:** Constructivism assumes that active learning will occur when learners enhance their knowledge by synthesis/new information with their prior knowledge. It suggests that students are more likely to learn when they seek out materials that relate to and elaborate their current knowledge. Therefore online learning material should provide multiple perspectives and representations of content. It is likely that a student's understanding and adaptability is increased when he/she is able to examine an experience from multiple perspectives. These perspectives provide the student with a greater opportunity to develop a more viable model of their experiences.
 - 3. Create communities of self directed learners:** Online technologies should not promote rote learning but encourage flexible exploration, divergent thinking, problem solving and extrapolation etc. These abilities will blossom rapidly when learning environment encourages learners to take responsibility of learning on their own shoulder. Thus information presented in online technology is likely to be strongly hierarchical; mirroring the reality of the external knowledge and presentation considerations giving attention to such issues as font size, use of colour and use of images in the belief that these will aid attention and foster knowledge retention.
 - 4. Promote student involvement:** Constructive learning to a great extent rests how well a student is engaged in the learning situation. Well designed systems should enhance student's perception of self efficacy and not detract from Therefore; learning atmosphere must be equipped with variety of leaning materials and resources. Further, learning materials presented through different multimedia i.e. www-hobs, internet technologies, net chat etc must be designed in such a manner that it will sustain the engagement of the students to a long duration rather than quick alienation.
 - 5. Support teaching and learning needs:** When educational technologies are developed from a purely pedagogical perspective, it is likely to support students needs in knowledge acquisition and generation. Simultaneously it is equally important that emergent systems also support teacher's needs. Students cannot be expected to benefit from technology if their teachers are neither familiar nor comfortable with it. Therefore we have to help teachers to learn not only how to use new technologies but also how to provide meaningful instruction and activities using technologies in classroom. A good system should enhance teacher's participation with students and support other teaching related issues.
 - 6. Be adaptable and flexible differentiated learning:** Online learning environment can be costly, complex and difficult to create and sustain. It is important that anticipated benefits are not negated by poor instructions, simple errors and technology failings. Therefore the emergent system must be adaptable so that teachers can ensure currency of the oil material provided. It is also important that they should be flexible to allow teachers to use these in teaching practices to suit different groups of students and learners to adapt them to their individual learning styles.
 - 7. Encouraged collaborative and cooperative learning:** Collaborative leaning has a major role in constructive cognitive development. This view assumes that learning is best facilitated through shared learning experiences among students as well as between students and teachers. In this context online learning environment is one of the best places for collaborative leaning. Therefore both the synchronous and asynchronous mode of electronic communication needs to be integrated meticulously in intensifying manner to open platform for healthy interaction between learners and peers and learners and teachers at anytime and anywhere.
- Supplement different feedback channel:** Use of online feedback can overcome the criticism of lack of feedback and direction provided to students. For example results of online quizzes can provide a nominal value that represents how well students understand particular concepts. The traditional and tutorial classes often do not benefit shy or less self assured students. The online feedback allows for teachers to support and monitor students' learning through the provision of appropriate feedback. This feedback is an important aspect of any students' performance and perceived self efficacy. The feedback should go beyond traditional communication of results and assessment feedback that support challenges and motives of the students.

Role of the Teacher: The process of instruction and role of instructor will help- to discover knowledge and provide expert feedback during knowledge building through structured collaborative learning tasks. Good constructivist proactively involves the teacher choosing appropriate elements of technologies i.e. communications, computer based simulations, using internet to find up-to-date information, spreadsheets for data analysis appropriate quiz etc to support learning These choices engage students in more active approaches to learning by using technology to stimulate their interest, curiosity, stimulate process and improve communication between student and student and teacher and student. The most successful teachers are those who use e technology in a more constructivist manner .Thus for extensive use of technologies, teacher may devise a series of more complicated project oriented activities relating to consequent themes, topics and tasks in various subject matters and implying a collaborative rather than competitive approach to problem solving.

Concluding Remarks: In conclusion the author would like to say that with the help of online learning technologies, there are ways and opportunities to make the above principles more realistic learning experiences, Further online leaning technologies encourage interactions, development of collaborative culture, utilization of active learning and introduction of feedback in proper context a well as bring abstract concepts to life by bringing into the teaching and learning the real world experiences through simulating, modelling, capturing and analyzing real events. Therefore learning from online learning technologies in conventional university campus *is* more reflective and will enhance retention power.The point must he made clear that online learning technologies should not be considered as a focal point for educational reform but rather resources to be integrated into a wide repertoire of educational resources.

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